

Climate, weather and Earth system models play a crucial role in understanding and predicting the Earth's climate system. The annual ACCESS Community Workshop aims to provide a platform for knowledge sharing and interdisciplinary collaboration around the science that uses the ACCESS models to address the complex Earth system challenges that Australia faces.

The 2024 ACCESS Community Workshop was held over 3-5 September 2023 online and in person at the Shine Dome, Australian Academy of Science, Canberra on Ngunnawal and Ngambri country.

The week kicked off with ACCESS-NRI's user training day (2 September) and concluded with 4 Community Working Group meetings on 5 of September.

Workshop Themes

In 2024, the Program Committee brought together people across all the ACCESS communities (Atmosphere, Ocean and sea-Ice, Land Surface, Earth System Modelling, Cryosphere, Machine Learning for climate and weather) to present and discuss current and emerging topics, both technical and scientific around the following broad themes:

- Model development and model evaluation for CMIP7
- High resolution modelling
- Paleoclimate and ice-sheet modelling

Workshop Aims

- Build community around the ACCESS models
- Showcase innovative science and modelling approaches
- Learn about new components developed for ACCESS
- Share knowledge between Community Working Groups and foster new and existing community-wide collaborations

Participants

We had 152 registrations for the workshop (116 in person, 36 virtual) from:

- Australian universities: University of New South Wales, University of Tasmania, Monash University, Australian National University, University of Melbourne, University of Adelaide.
- National scientific organisations: CSIRO, Bureau of Meteorology, National Environmental Science Program (NESP), ARC Centre of Excellence for Climate Extremes (CLEX), Australian Antarctic Division (AAD), Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies (IMAS), ARC Centre of Excellence for Weather of the 21st Century, Australian Centre for Excellence in Antarctic Science (ACEAS), Australian Antarctic Program Partnership, ARC Special Research Initiative *Securing Antarctica's Environmental Future*.
- Government representatives: Climate Change Authority.
- International universities and scientific institutions: Met Office (UK), Atmosphere and Ocean Research Institute, AORI, University of Tokyo (Japan); National Institute for Space Research, INPE (Brazil).
- Research infrastructures: ACCESS-NRI, NCI.
- Other: Haizea Analytics.

Program

The workshop included 19 science and technical talks, 15 lightning presentations and 39 posters from the ACCESS community as well as 5 invited keynote speakers. The full workshop program including recordings of all the plenary talks and links to the ACCESS-Hive Forum discussions can be found in the link below:

[FULL PROGRAM](#)

Day 1

Day 1 of the workshop opened with a welcome to country by Ngunnawal elder, Richie Allan, followed by an Introductions and ACCESS Science Update by ACCESS-NRI Director, Andy Hogg.

Our first keynote speaker was **Tomoki Miyakawa** (Atmosphere and Ocean Research Institute, AORI, University of Tokyo) on “The current status of global high-resolution modelling activities” followed by a session of invited science and Community or infrastructure talks and a Lightning talks session.

The day also included a keynote presentation by **Felicity McCormack** (Monash University and ARC Special Research Initiative *Securing Antarctica’s*

Environmental Future) on “An introduction to ACCESS' ice sheet model: the Ice-sheet and Sea Level System Model (ISSM)”.

The day closed with a keynote talk by **Birgit Hassler** (German Aerospace Centre DLR) closed Day 1 with her keynote presentation on “ESMValTool: Analyzing CMIP-style data made easy”.

Day 2

Day 2 was opened by **Richard Jones** (Met Office, UK) on “K-Scale: A global to regional model hierarchy for assessing the costs and benefits of high-resolution global simulations.”

Breakout sessions were the focus for Day 2 and included 8 discussion topics. These topics were proposed by the ACCESS community and selected to bring together people with shared interests

across the diverse community. The discussion included sharing the status of current work, capturing future ACCESS community needs and identifying areas in need of support. Detailed summaries of the individual breakout discussion groups can be found in the Appendix 2.

1. **Evaluation of ENSO and climate metrics in ACCESS for CMIP7 and beyond.** Co-chairs: Christine Chung, (Bureau of Meteorology) and Harun Rashid (CSIRO)
2. **Goings on at the Antarctic margins: ocean circulation, ice shelves, and sea ice.** Chair: Ed Doddridge (UTAS)
3. **Urban representation (dataset and parameterization) in ACCESS-NRI land models.** Co-chairs: Negin Nazarian, Matthew Lipson and Jiachen Lu (UNSW)
4. **High resolution modelling.** Co-chairs: Clothilde Langlais and Chris Chapman (CSIRO)
5. **Regional climate modelling and ancillary generation for the nesting suite in the UM.** Chair: Emma Howard (Bureau of Meteorology).
6. **6. Emulation of climate model output using machine learning or other data driven approaches.** Chair: Vassili Kitsios (CSIRO)
7. **Paleoclimate and idealised modelling in the ACCESS suite of models.** Chair: David Hutchinson (UNSW)
8. **Visualising Earth systems data.** Co-chairs: Paige Martin and Owen Kaluza (ACCESS-NRI)

Day 2 closed with a keynote talk by **Sebastian Steinig** (University of Bristol, UK) on “climatearchive.org”: 500 million years of climate data at your fingertips”

Day 3

Day 3 of the Workshop started with an introduction to the Community Working Group (CWG) meetings and a reflection of the first two days by ACCESS-NRI Associate Director, Kelsey Druken. This was followed by the presentation of the best poster awards, which attendees voted on through the [online poster gallery](#). They winners included:

- **Best Student Poster (and Best overall):** *Jemma Jeffree (ANU) for [“Connecting daily weather to monthly SST”](#)*
- **1st place:** Ben Schroeter (ACCESS-NRI) for [“Connecting evaluation tools across the LSM community: ME.org Client + HPCPy”](#)
- **2nd place:** Farhan Rizwi et al (CSIRO) for [“COMPAS A coastal unstructured ocean model using Voronoi meshes”](#)
- **3rd place:** Jasmeen Kaur (ACCESS-NRI) for [“What is the ACCESS-Hive?”](#)

Community Working Group meetings

This year, we had four Community Working group meetings on the 3rd day of the Workshop. These included the new Working Group *Machine learning for climate and weather* that replaced the *Forecasting and Prediction* Working Group.

	Earth System Modelling (ESM) Working Group – link to Program
	Atmosphere Working Group – link to Program
	Cryosphere Working Group – link to Program
	Machine Learning for Climate and Weather Working Group – link to Program

Overall summary

A major focus of the 2024 workshop was continued community building and support for the community Working Groups (WGs). We had 5 excellent keynote speakers, including three international speakers. The science talks showcased the diverse research that is enabled by the ACCESS models, while the ACCESS-NRI technical talks presented to the community both current and future focus of the ACCESS-NRI team. In addition to the Director's ACCESS Science Update, ACCESS-NRI had 12 presentations (4 talks, 8 lightning talks) and 13 posters.

Breakout sessions included constructive discussion on cross-cutting community topics proposed by the ACCESS Community.

The breakouts raised awareness of shared areas of interest, current work occurring across the community and areas for future collaboration.

The workshop received very positive feedback with 97% of survey responses¹ finding this year's workshop valuable. The most valuable aspects reported included the talks, opportunities for interactions and collaborations and bringing people together and learning about the latest developments across the diverse community. Networking and the mix of software/infrastructure and science talks, including the keynote speakers and cross-group breakout sessions, were also commonly noted favourably in the responses.

We also received many helpful suggestions that will help improve future workshops, including having a dedicated poster session (separate from networking), less keynote talks and more shorter talks and encouraging more participation of ECR and students. Planning for the 2025 workshop is already underway and the ACCESS-NRI team looks forward to working with the community and incorporating this feedback into next year's event.

¹ Workshop survey received 43 responses.
2024 ACCESS Community Workshop Report

Acknowledgements

We at ACCESS-NRI acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the land on which our research infrastructure and community operate across Australia and pay our respects to Elders past and present. We recognise the thousands of years of accumulated knowledge and deep connection they have with all the Earth systems we simulate.

Thank you to our partners, ACCESS-NRI team and members of the ACCESS community for their contributions throughout the workshop and related events. We also thank the Program Committee members Andy Hogg (Chair, ACCESS-NRI), David Hutchinson (UNSW), Emma Howard (Bureau of Meteorology), Jasmeen Kaur (ACCESS-NRI), Julie Arblaster (Monash University), Tammás Loughran (CSIRO) and Natalia Bateman (ACCESS-NRI) for their valuable contributions, time and help making this a successful workshop. Finally, thanks to Harshula Jayasuriya for the photography during the workshop.

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APPENDIX 1: Workshop Attendees

Figure 1. Reported organisations of the registered participants.

Figure 2. Report roles of the registered participants.

Figure 3. Reported career stages of the registered participants.

Figure 4. (a) Reported experience with ACCESS models, components, or configurations from registered participants. (b) Reported experience with ACCESS related data (model outputs or inputs).

APPENDIX 2: Breakout Sessions

The following section includes session descriptions of the breakout discussions held at this year's annual workshop. Each session also includes links to corresponding ACCESS-Hive Forum topics and to the shared documents used to capture notes during the discussions.

Session 1

Breakout 1: Evaluation of ENSO and climate metrics in ACCESS for CMIP7 and beyond. Co-chairs: Christine Chung, (Bureau of Meteorology) and Harun Rashid (CSIRO)

Description: Comprehensive evaluation of climate and earth system models is essential for advancing scientific research and improvements in climate modelling. A new version of the Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator (ACCESS) is now being developed for participation in the upcoming Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) phase 7. This breakout session aims to discuss and explore:

- the methodology and target variables, diagnostics, and climate driver metrics to be used for evaluations of the next generation ACCESS and other CMIP7 models.
- the scope and potential benefits of process-based model evaluations, with an emphasis on El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO).
- bridging the gap between evaluation studies and model development - making model evaluations more useful for model improvements.

[Link to Shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Breakout 2: Goings on at the Antarctic margins: ocean circulation, ice shelves, and sea ice. Chair: Ed Doddridge (UTAS)

Description: The Antarctic margins are where ocean, sea ice, and ice sheets come together. It is a region of rapidly unfolding changes (e.g. sea ice loss and ocean warming) and key challenges for future research (e.g. ice shelf cavity circulations, coupled ocean - ice sheet processes).

The next generation of coupled models aim to include interactive coupling between these different physical components. This breakout session is intended as a forum to discuss both the scientific questions such models will allow us to ask, and the technical challenges of this coupling.

[Link to Shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Breakout 3. Urban representation (dataset and parameterization) in ACCESS-NRI land models. Co-chairs: Negin Nazarian, Matthew Lipson and Jiachen Lu (UNSW)

Description: Urban areas, as the most extreme case of natural landscape modification, are often underrepresented in regional and global climate models or reanalysis datasets. Within the ACCESS-NRI land models, the Joint UK Land Environment Simulator (JULES) includes a medium-complexity urban canopy model to treat cities, while the Community Atmosphere Biosphere Land Exchange (CABLE) currently lacks any urban representation or parameterization. This breakout session will explore the advancements proposed for CABLE, focusing on integrating urban datasets and physics into the model. It also aims to consult the community on:

- **Research Interests:** Identifying key research questions that could benefit from enhanced urban representations and modelling within the ACCESS-NRI framework.
- **Current and Future Needs:** Evaluating the data and modelling requirements necessary to effectively represent urban environments in climate models, both now and in the future.

[Link to Shared created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Breakout 4. High resolution modelling. Co-chairs: Clothilde Langlais and Chris Chapman (CSIRO)

Description: There is a clear movement of the community towards simulations at higher and higher resolutions. While exciting, high resolution simulations have many challenges, scientific, technical, and on a community management level.

How do we come together as a community to address joint challenges across domains (atmosphere, ocean, land-surface, cryosphere)? Are there easily identifiable “low hanging fruit”? What does a “high resolution” community look like?

[Link to Shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Session 2

Breakout 5: Regional climate modelling and ancillary generation for the nesting suite in the UM. Chair: Emma Howard (Bureau of Meteorology)

Description: This breakout session will examine the technical aspects of setting up UM for regional experiments, focussing on timescales beyond short-term forecasts. The aim is to share recent suite development activities and discuss future plans in order to share knowledge and avoid the duplication of work. Topics include nesting in BARRA-R2 reanalysis, new Australia-specific ancillaries, and online suite monitoring.

[Link to shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Breakout 6. Emulation of climate model output using machine learning or other data driven approaches. Chair: Vassili Kitsios (CSIRO)

Description: Reduced-order models of the climate, or climate emulators, approximate the dynamics of the climate in a computationally cheap fashion as compared to a full complexity general circulation model (GCM). These reduced-order models can be developed from fundamental principles by instead representing a lower dimensional system. They can also be developed using machine learning, statistical learning or a variety of other data-driven methods, which exploit existing GCM output, reanalysis data, or real-world observations. Computationally cheap climate emulators will enable: a more complete assessment of climate risk for a broader range of climate emissions scenarios; and exploration of science questions and methods development via a hierarchy of representative models.

[Link to shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Breakout 7. Paleoclimate and idealised modelling in the ACCESS suite of models. Chair: David Hutchinson (UNSW)

Description: Discussion about current progress and outstanding challenges in paleoclimate and idealised coupled climate modelling using the ACCESS models. There has been significant progress over the past year in developing novel topographies in ACCESS-ESM1.5. But, several aspects of the model remain difficult to manage for many users.

[Link to shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)

Breakout 8. Visualising Earth systems data. Co-chairs: Paige Martin and Owen Kaluza (ACCESS-NRI)

Description: Do you want to learn about the available visualisation tools for Earth systems? Or do you want to learn how to do 3-d data visualisation? Or maybe you'd like to refine your 2-d visualisation skills with a particular tool? Join us for a community discussion on data visualisation! We will kick off the session with a demo of one particular example of data visualisation from Owen Kaluza, and then discuss community needs and desires for data viz moving forward.

Goal of this session: To decide as a group which data visualisation tools are of most interest to the ACCESS community and what next steps would best support data visualisation needs/interests within the community

[Link to shared document created during the session](#)

[Link to discussion on the Hive Forum](#)